

6GSMART P1-P1-D1.1
Revisión del estado del arte y diseño
inicial del cloud continuo de 6GSMART
v1.0

Fecha de Publicación: 28/07/2023
6GSMART-ICC

Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión –
6G I+D

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	6GSMART-SP1-L2
Líder del PT	ATOS
Editor Principal	Borja Otura García
Contribuyentes	Borja Otura García
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
1.0	Borja Otura García	Entregado	28/07/2023	

1 Table of Contents

1	Table of Contents	3
2	List of Figures	4
3	List of Acronyms	5
4	Executive Summary	7
5	Introduction	8
	5.1 Objectives	8
6	State of the Art Review	9
	6.1 Cloud-continuum integration	9
	6.2 Research initiatives	13
7	Preliminary System Architecture	19
	7.1 High-level requirements	19
	7.2 Concept and General Architecture	20
8	Summary and conclusions	25

2 List of Figures

Figure 1. 6G SNS JU Interlinking of Streams into Phases	14
Figure 2. Meta-Operating Systems for the Next-Generation IoT and Edge Computing	17
Figure 3. EU Cloud-Edge-IoT Task Forces	18
Figure 4. Preliminary CORC General Architecture	21

3 List of Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet Of Things Innovation
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
CORC	Continuum ORChestrator
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
E2E	End-to-End
EU/UE	European Union
EUCEI	EU Cloud Edge IoT
FENS	Factory Edge Network Service
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSMA	GSM (Groupe Spéciale Mobile) Association
I4.0	Industry 4.0
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IIoT	Industrial Internet Of Things
IT	Information Technology
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LST&P	Large Scale Trials and Pilots
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
ML	Machine Learning
NPN	Non-Public Networks
NSaaS	Network Slicing as a Service
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OP	Operator Platform
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
PLC	Programmable Logic Controllers
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDN	Software Define Networks
SDO	Standards Developing Organizations
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SNS JU	Software Networks & Services Joint Undertaking
SSID	Service Set Identifier
TAC	Tracking Area Code
UN	United Nations

UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
US	United States
VM	Virtual Machine
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
WG	Working Group
XR	Extended Reality

4 Executive Summary

6GSMART-ICC Project studies the application of 6G in the manufacturing area, with a focus on the orchestration of the cloud-continuum in industrial use cases that leverage the integration of resources in the public and private domains. The project is framed under the *Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia* of the Spanish Government that channels the *Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)* funding of *NextGenerationEU*.

The new technologies introduced in 5G networks, such as Network Function Virtualization, Multi-access Edge Computing and Software Defined Networks have changed the ecosystem and the way telco services are consumed from general public to vertical industries like manufacturing. There are, however, new challenges introduced in the management of the increased availability of hyper-distributed computing resources at different tiers of the network. This availability enables application developers to design innovative solutions that leverage the new service offering, but a gap exists between the developers focused on the challenges of the vertical specific solutions and the complexities of next generation networks. The upcoming 6G technology is required to take on this challenge and facilitate the interaction of vertical applications with 6G networks.

The deployment of vertical applications across multiple tiers in the cloud continuum require specific approaches for each component orchestration depending on the target tier such as an adequate categorization of the resources or dynamic mechanisms for discovery and management of volatile devices in the extreme edge to be implemented to complete the end-to-end integration between extreme edge, edge and cloud.

This document first presents a study of the State of the Art, in particular the works under the scope of research initiatives like the 6G SNS JU¹ or EUCloudEdgeIoT². Then, a system architecture that takes on the challenges of Cloud Continuum orchestration between public and private domains from the perspective of application developers is described.

¹ 6G SNS JU Website - <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/>

² <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

5 Introduction

This document provides a report on the State of the Art review on the Cloud Continuum concept and the considerations for large scale implementation of hyper-distributed applications from the perspective of application developers and presents a preliminary system architecture design of a Cloud Continuum orchestration framework.

This document is the results of project task *6GSMART-SP1-L2-T1.1.2: Revisión del estado del arte y diseño inicial del cloud continuo de 6GSMART, bajo la perspectiva de un desarrollador de tecnologías cloud* described in the project's execution plan. The work reported on this document serves as a basis of work towards a final architecture that will be reported on deliverables *6GSMART P1-P1-D1.2 "Diseño final y evaluación del cloud continuo de 6GSMART"* and *6GSMART P2-P1-D2.2 "Diseño final y evaluación de la solución para integración de redes públicas y privadas en 6GSMART"*.

5.1 Objectives

The first objective of this document is to present a review on the Cloud Continuum concept, the current trends, and advancements in the topic of orchestration across the continuum and the latest and more innovative research initiatives in the topic.

Furthermore, based on the results of this State of the Art, the second objective is to present a preliminary system architecture that satisfies the needs of application developers and integrators that rely on such systems to obtain straightforward access the resources and capabilities of a flexible, distributed, and high-performance heterogeneous infrastructure.

6 State of the Art Review

In recent years, the proliferation of cloud computing and the advent of 5G technology have revolutionized the digital landscape, enabling unprecedented connectivity and computing capabilities. As we approach the next generation of wireless communication, 6G, the integration of multiple cloud services at different tiers within the network infrastructure is poised to play a pivotal role in shaping future advancements. This section delves into the state of the art regarding the integration of the resources of these clouds into a cloud continuum, focusing on the perspective of cloud application developers.

Cloud continuum integration refers to the seamless convergence of heterogeneous cloud resources available at different tiers such as cloud, edge and extreme edge, enabling enhanced computing, storage, and network capabilities for a wide range of applications. From the perspective of cloud application developers, this integration offers an array of possibilities, providing access to powerful computing resources and enabling the development of highly scalable and efficient applications. By leveraging the cloud continuum, developers can harness the potential of edge computing, distributed storage, to create innovative and responsive applications that meet the ever-increasing demands of the digital era.

This section explores the key aspects and challenges of cloud continuum integration in 5G towards 6G. Furthermore, we discuss emerging technologies and research initiatives that aim to address these challenges and drive the future evolution of cloud continuum integration in the 6G era.

Through an examination of current trends, research advancements, and industry practices, this section seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the state of the art in cloud continuum integration in 5G towards 6G from the perspective of cloud application developers. By understanding the opportunities and challenges presented by this integration, developers can better navigate the evolving landscape and unlock the full potential of cloud-based applications in the future digital ecosystem.

6.1 Cloud-continuum integration

To talk about what is understood by Cloud Continuum, it is necessary to establish what is understood by Cloud³. The term Cloud refers to the provision of computing resources in a pooled manner, providing independence in the management of these resources from their usage, favouring deployment flexibility and cost savings. However, there is not only a single Cloud, and different types can be grouped based on certain criteria.

First, it is necessary to group them based on the ownership of the resources. We have private Cloud when the offered resources belong to the entity that will use them, and public Cloud when an entity manages resources that are then leased to third parties. The major hyperscale public Cloud providers in 2022 are Amazon Web Services (AWS),

³ The Cloud Continuum. Sept2021. <https://www.architectureandgovernance.com/app-tech/the-cloud-continuum/>

Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Microsoft Azure⁴, although there are many other Cloud service providers⁵. Furthermore, we have hybrid Cloud models when the two aforementioned concepts are combined, and multi-Cloud when multiple public Cloud providers are combined.

After this classification, we can make a categorization based on the services offered. Under the umbrella of the general term XaaS⁶ (Everything-as-a-Service), we have IaaS (Infrastructure-as-a-Service), PaaS (Platform-as-a-Service), and SaaS (Software-as-a-Service). IaaS is the lowest level of service where the user has control over managing the infrastructure needed to deploy their application using the provided hardware abstraction. PaaS offers a higher level of abstraction and allows developers to deploy their applications without worrying about the underlying infrastructure. Finally, SaaS provides direct access to pre-developed and deployed applications, allowing easy integration with the user's application through APIs (Application Programming Interfaces).

Another classification can be made regarding the location of resources, where closer resources offer higher performance, especially in terms of latency, compared to more distant resources. Given the speed of light magnitude, which would enable low latencies between two systems connected by direct fibre even over long distances, we refer to proximity and distance here, not only geographically but also considering network topology and the "number of hops" between these systems. We then have resources at the Edge⁷ of the infrastructure when there are demanding latency requirements or a need to reduce backhaul transmission costs. If we take to the extreme the concept of edge, we end up at the Extreme Edge or Far Edge, that we can group in its own category and it is the closest to the user, even on the user side of the access network. The rest of the resources, without such requirements, are simply referred to as the Central Cloud or the Core, or simply the Cloud.

This is where the concept of Cloud Continuum comes into play, referring to the seamless and fluid integration of different Clouds. As we have seen, different types of Cloud offer different capabilities, and developers and telecommunication service providers need to consider the pros and cons of each when using them efficiently. However, until now, the convergence of different Cloud environments has required manual configuration, and there is a need for an environment that allows for the unified orchestration of End-to-End (E2E) applications across different services offered by public and private Cloud providers, both in the core and at the edge, available to the user.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to study the possibility of creating an abstraction of the available resources through each provider so that applications can be defined using a common language like an intent, regardless of the infrastructure on which they run or the provider that manages it. This End-to-End application definition requires an orchestrator with the ability to interact with public cloud providers, orchestrate applications and resources in private clouds, as well as create interconnections between

⁴ Global Cloud services spend <https://canalys.com/newsroom/global-cloud-services-Q2-2022>

⁵ HFS research. Hyperscalers Cloud providers March 2021 - <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/LYZX6JB5>

⁶ XaaS's three pillars: SaaS, IaaS and PaaS. RCWireless research'22. <https://www.rcwireless.com/20220114/telco-cloud/xaass-three-pillars-saas-iaas-and-paas>

⁷ ATOS SC – A 2021 perspective on Edge Computing <https://atos.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/atos-2021-perspective-on-edge-computing-white-paper.pdf>

different domains through Software-Defined Networks (SDN), maintaining a global view of the infrastructures and services at their disposal. Mobile network operators and transmission network operators can be considered connectivity providers for these applications in different sections, such as cellular access to edge and core clouds, communications between edge and extreme edge clouds, and communications between edge clouds and the cloud core. In this way, the proposed abstraction can include not only the necessary computing resources for each part of the application but also communications with other services within the application that have been deployed in different clouds, as well as performance requirements in device access to the application.

This ecosystem extends and deepens the business model presented by 3GPP regarding NSaaS (Network Slicing as a Service) by integrating it with the Cloud XaaS service model. The model under study would allow developers to interact with all ecosystem actors from a single platform. In the applied case of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) environments, companies would have the tools to deploy their own applications designed specifically for their production processes and needs while using services from their own IT facilities, thus guaranteeing the security of their most sensitive data, combined with third-party services hosted on remote public clouds⁸. The NPN (Non-Public Networks) model presented by 3GPP in its version 16 allows public network operators to deploy services equivalent to virtual private networks through their public 5G infrastructure or dedicated infrastructure deployed to cover, in this case, the access needs of the production plant. This completes a system of federated resources that allows for End-to-End deployment of applications with Edge performance capabilities, while maintaining the flexibility and capacity of the cloud (without the characteristic limitations of the Edge) for components of the application that do not have such requirements.

Industry 4.0 is a paradigm shift in manufacturing, focused on the creation of intelligent factories based on cyber-physical systems (CPS), a technology that merges computing, communication, and control (sensors, actuators, etc.). In a broad sense, it is a system of physical devices integrated into a controllable, reliable, and scalable network that integrates computing, communication, and control capabilities based on environmental knowledge. This integration enables real-time interaction through a feedback loop, where computational and physical processes interact with each other to add or expand new functions and monitor or control a physical entity securely, reliably, efficiently, and in real-time. For this, 6G technology will be key in industrial environments, allowing the manufacturing industry to transition to I4.0 since communications are the backbone for the smooth operation of industrial processes and the proper exchange of data between devices and services.

The coexistence of existing industrial wireless networks and the new capabilities in b5G/6G^{9,10} networks are considered a key element for future intelligent industrial processes due to the strict latency requirements of control systems and many Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) applications, which condition the deployment of the latter in the

⁸ GSMA 5G IoT private networks for Industry 4.0 - <https://www.gsma.com/iot/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-10-GSMA-5G-IoT-Private-and-Dedicated-Networks-for-Industry-4.0.pdf>

⁹ 6G white paper 5GIA - <https://5g-ppp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/WhitePaper-6G-Europe.pdf>

¹⁰ Nokia Bell Labs, "Communications in the Era of 6G," White Paper, 2020, <https://onestore.nokia.com/asset/207766>

same production plant. Similarly, security requirements such as confidentiality, integrity, and availability of services require keeping IIoT communications completely local. Edge clouds (i.e., storage and processing computational resources at the edge of the network) address these requirements.

In an I4.0 ecosystem, the use of an NPN integrating multiple types of networks¹¹ allows for an end-to-end network so that private traffic can be confined within the defined facility boundaries without reaching the public domain. Thus, an industrial NPN 6G network solution will provide an integrated ecosystem based on industrial hardware with dedicated access, as well as software modules of the core network providing increased security and control in data management, broadband speeds, deterministic behaviour, real-time response, and cost efficiency to factories deploying AI-driven IIoT applications, allowing for a larger number of sensors and instrumentation and control equipment, as well as critical business applications within their facilities. This is achieved based on extremely low latency and high reliability.

The continuity of cloud at the edge (Cloud to Edge continuum) offered by 6G networks is therefore crucial for smart manufacturing, providing the necessary mechanisms to avoid transporting captured data from industrial processes and monitoring from the production plant to the cloud. Instead, this data can be analysed in-depth at a large scale, leveraging the computational power and resource flexibility offered by a remote cloud infrastructure. Processing this data at the edge of the cloud while avoiding security issues when exchanging information between different certified industrial data providers.

The *Report on Computing Continuum Scenarios, Requirements and Optical Communication enablers*¹² by the *Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI) WG Standardisation* assesses several use cases across multiple industrial applications and identifies (supported on existing literature¹³) a set of requirements for the Cloud Continuum¹⁴ required to interconnect resources across cloud, edge and devices. These requirements are mainly:

- High performance network bandwidth with flexible and dynamic allocation to cater for different use case needs.
- High reliability combined with ultra-low latency to support the ever-increasing use cases supporting mission critical applications such as medical. In some cases, direct optical communications are required.
- Data security and privacy at every layer to guarantee the protection of the traversing operating and personal data from unauthorized access. This is very tightly related to the requirement of trust on the computing facilities.
- Support for real-time applications.

¹¹ Tezcan Cogalan, Daniel Camps, Jesus Guitierrez et al. IEEE Communications Magazine Feb 22: 5G-CLARITY: 5G-Advanced Private Networks Integrating 5G NR, WiFi, and LiFi - DOI:10.1109/MCOM.001.2100615

¹² <https://aioti.eu/aioti-wg-standardisation-report-computing-continuum-scenarios-requirements-and-optical-communication-enablers/>

¹³ Wazir Zada Khan, Ejaz Ahmed, Saqib Hakak, Ibrar Yaqoob, Arif Ahmed, "Edge Computing: A Survey", Elsevier, Future Generation Computer Systems, Volume 97, August © All rights reserved, Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI) 2022 31 2019, Pages 219-235. see: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X18319903>

¹⁴ The report focuses on optical network communications but the requirements are general for the Cloud Continuum.

- A unified business model that enables the utilization of services across multiple providers.
- Dynamic resource management across multiple domains.
- Scalability to support the increasing number of devices and services at the edge.
- Service discovery, delivery and mobility is a key requirement to support the integration of far edge devices in the continuum.
- Seamless coordination of heterogeneous resources and devices.

6.2 Research initiatives

Taking over from 5GPPP, the European 6G Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (6G SNS JU¹⁵) is a Public-Private Partnership focused on advancing European industrial leadership in 5G and 6G networks and services. Its main goals are to drive research and innovation (R&I) for 6G technology, aiming for standardization by 2025, and to boost 5G deployment across Europe for digital market development and the transition to a digital and green economy. The SNS JU coordinates programs, provides strategic guidance, and facilitates collaboration among stakeholders to achieve these objectives.

The first Work program of the SNS JU was launched in 2021 with the goal to promote this leadership and autonomy of the European industry pioneering the global digital and green transition. The work program sets the concrete requirements to support the alignment with United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)¹⁶ and specifically to SDG 8 (sustainable economic growth), SDG 9 (sustainable industry, innovation, and resilient infrastructure), SDG 11 (sustainable cities and communities) and SDG 13 (climate action).

To achieve its targets, the work program¹⁷ is structured in 4 streams that extend across three phases with clear distinct focuses: 5G Evolution (Stream A), 6G Development (Stream B), Experimental Infrastructure (Stream C) and Vertical Pilots (Stream D). These streams, however, are not expected to work as silos, but rather feed into each other with the ultimate goal to foster and help develop the European ecosystem that will lead 6G technologies and innovation.

¹⁵ 6G SNS JU Website - <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

Figure 1. 6G SNS JU Interlinking of Streams into Phases¹⁷

Within each of the Streams, the work is subdivided in multiple strands that focus the different activities around specific technological advancements or expected outputs. In this way the main strands that are relevant to 6GSMART are:

- SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-05: Edge Computing Evolution:
 - This strand focuses on the evolution of virtualization taking place at multiple segments into a distributed set of optimized computing resources in a continuum that meets certain requirements in terms of performance such as latency, capacity, etc. and supports multiple edge/Access scenarios. The project *AI-powered eVolution towards opEn and secuRe edGe archiEctures (VERGE)*¹⁸ is funded under this strand with the aim to tackle the challenges of the distributed edge integration with a focus on AI-assisted management and orchestration solutions and the security, privacy and trustworthiness of the AI models deployed at the edge.
- SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-07: Real-time Zero-touch Service Technologies:
 - The objective of this strand is to support vertical application developers by studying deployment and management mechanisms that ease the interaction between the Telco and IT worlds in an automated way and with special attention to reducing deployment's power consumption and increasing efficiency. The project *Automated zero-touch cross-layer provisioning framework for 5G and beyond vertical services (ACROSS)*¹⁹ has been granted funding to carry out its proposal. The ACROSS project aims to provide an advanced platform for next-gen network and service deployment. It focuses on automation, performance, scalability, and energy efficiency. The platform includes distributed orchestrators, deep telemetry, AI-driven intelligence, zero-touch provisioning, and secure

¹⁷ ANNEX II to the 2023 SNS Work Programme 2023 SNS R&I Work Programme for 2023-2024 - https://smart-networks.europa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/sns_ri_wp_2023-24.pdf

¹⁸ <https://www.verge-project.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101097122>

- orchestration mechanisms. ACROSS aims to submit proof-of-concept projects to standards and open-source initiatives.
- SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-01: System Architecture:
 - The projects funded under this strand aim to support the worlds ever increasing hyperconnectivity and digitalization requirements focusing on the unified service provisioning across diverse domains and heterogeneous resources. The target is to create an architecture for extreme 6G use cases, inter-computing capabilities, and programmable connectivity across different domains. Four initiatives have been funded under this topic: *Distributed Artificial Intelligence-driven open and programmable architecture for 6G networks (ADROIT6G)*²⁰, software driven integration of AI-managed heterogeneous cloud-native networks; *Deep Programmability and Secure Distributed Intelligence for Real-Time End-to-End 6G Networks (DESIRE6G)*²¹, zero-touch management and orchestration platform with a focus on near real-time automations that support ultra-low latency cloud native applications in a multitenant environment; *DETERMINISTIC E2E COMMUNICATION WITH 6G (DETERMINISTIC6G)*²², leveraging digital twin concept to provide a novel architecture allowing the creation and utilization of a deterministic view of the performance of an heterogeneous network; *Programmable AI-Enabled Deterministic Networking for 6G (PREDICT-6G)*²³ aims to develop a secure and modular network framework that automates end-to-end services across multiple domains, ensuring consistent E2E determinism.
 - SNS-2022-STREAM-B-01-05: 6G Holistic System:
 - The project funded under this strand aim to develop a comprehensive end-to-end system framework for 6G networks, integrating key results from various 5G PPP strands and other 6G initiatives. It focuses on societal and technical aspects, identifying key use cases, technologies, and critical areas for future standardization work to address citizen needs in 2030 and beyond. *Hexa-X-II project (A holistic flagship towards the 6G network platform and system, to inspire digital transformation, for the world to act together in meeting needs in society and ecosystems with novel 6G services)* leads the development of end-to-end system design and an enabling platform for novel services in the next generation (6G) wireless networks, building on the results obtained from the previous phase flagship project Hexa-X.
 - SNS-2022-STREAM-C-01-01: SNS experimental Infrastructure:
 - Create an evolvable experimental infrastructure demonstrating key 6G candidate technologies and beyond 5G performance benchmarks, while validating security, multi-access edge computing with a focus on energy efficient continuum, spectrum technologies, and end-to-end architectures, in support of innovative use cases and societal objectives. Three projects received funding under this strand and will aim to offer open experimentation and the creation of a pan-European platform that

²⁰ <https://adroit6g.eu/>

²¹ <https://desire6g.eu/>

²² <https://deterministic6g.eu/>

²³ <https://predict-6g.eu/>

integrates the testbeds and can serve as basis for the large-scale trials to take place on Stream D projects: *6G-BRICKS*²⁴ *Building Reusable testbed Infrastructures for validating Cloud-to-device breakthrough technologies*; *Supporting Architectural and technological Network evolutions through an intelligent, secureD and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation facility (6G-SANDBOX)*²⁵; and *6G eXperimental Research infrastructure to enable next-generation XR services (6G-XR)*²⁶.

- SNS-2022-STREAM-D-01-01: SNS Large Scale Trials and Pilots (LST&Ps) with Verticals:
 - The project aims to contribute to sustainable 5G and 6G test infrastructures, validate core technologies in large-scale pilot use-cases, develop viable business models, impact standardization bodies, showcase Europe's 5G evolution, and stimulate industrial engagement in 6G experimentation. It also aims to create a repository of requirements, open-source tools, and modules, as well as collect new requirements related to emerging application domains, edge computing, distributed networks, AI integration, and trustworthiness for public and private networks and applications. The projects that obtained funding under this topic are: *Field Trials beyond 5G (FIDAL)*²⁷; *Advanced 5G Open Platform for Large Scale Trials and Pilots across Europe (IMAGINE-B5G)*²⁸; *Trial Platform for 5G Evolution – Cross-Industry On Large Scale (TARGET-X)*²⁹; *TRials supported by Smart Networks beyond 5G (TrialsNet)*³⁰. These projects will form a European ecosystem of evolvable advanced 5G and 6G open infrastructures for testing prototypes across multiple verticals at a large scale.

Other European initiatives around cloud, edge and IoT convergence are funded under the *Horizon Europe -Work Programme 2021-2022 for Digital, Industry and Space*³¹. In particular, under call *HORIZON-CL4-2021-DATA-01-05: “Future European platforms for the Edge: Meta Operating Systems (RIA)”* with the objective to promote the development of Meta Operating systems that enable the convergence of cloud, edge and IoT domains by leveraging the connectivity provided by next-generation communication networks.

²⁴ <https://6g-bricks.eu/>

²⁵ <https://6g-sandbox.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.6g-xr.eu/>

²⁷ <https://fidal-he.eu/>

²⁸ <https://imagineb5g.eu/>

²⁹ <https://target-x.eu/>

³⁰ <https://trialsnet.eu/>

³¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2022/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-7-digital-industry-and-space_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

Figure 2. Meta-Operating Systems for the Next-Generation IoT and Edge Computing³²

Six projects are funded by this grant:

- The aerOS³³ project aims to create an IoT-edge-cloud continuum by developing a virtualized, platform-agnostic meta operating system. This system will transparently utilize resources on the different tiers of the computing continuum to enable effective applications. The distribution of intelligence and computation, including AI, ML, and big data analytics is key aspect of aerOS service optimization goals. The project will deliver common virtualized services, offer a flexible and resilient API, and include infrastructural services for cybersecurity, trustworthiness, and manageability.
- FLUIDOS³⁴ (Flexible, scaLable, secUre, and decentralliseD Operating System) objective is to create an inter-domain cloud meta-OS that can take advantage of the unused processing capabilities of heterogeneous end devices in the network by building on top of existing orchestration systems like Kubernetes and aiming to focus on low cost, energy efficiency and security.
- NebulOuS³⁵ meta-OS will extend the concept of computing OS to the cloud to provide a transparent fabric of computation across the continuum, creating slice-like clouds by brokering the resources offered by different providers.
- NEMO³⁶ focuses on enabling on-device intelligence to massive AI-enabled IoT applications through an intent-based, open, modular, and secure meta-Operating System.
- NEPHELE³⁷ project is based on the creation of a software platform to integrate the computing resources of heterogeneous devices into the virtualization

³² https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/repository/document/2022-25/Factsheet_Horizon_Europe_metaOS_projects_8aBnKLIInqjY1Epj4HlvU4vzIY_87827.pdf

³³ <https://aeros-project.eu/>

³⁴ <https://www.fluidos.eu/>

³⁵ <https://www.nebulouscloud.eu/>

³⁶ <https://meta-os.eu/>

³⁷ <https://nephele-project.eu/>

capabilities of the cloud continuum to enable hyper-distributed applications following the “system of systems” approach.

These 6 projects are part of the EU Cloud-Edge-IoT (EUCEI)³⁸ which aims to host a space for research and innovation clusters studying and developing the technology to share advancements and discuss approaches with the goal to create a dynamic ecosystem that provides strategic guidance and a technical leadership, linking developers with markets and establishing common architectures and standards.

To achieve its goal the initiative is structured in task forces that focus on specific areas: Strategic Liaisons, Open-Source Engagement, Architecture, Ecosystem Engagement, Market & Sectors and Communications.

Figure 3. EU Cloud-Edge-IoT Task Forces³⁹

Atos leads the Architecture task force which objective is to serve as a common point of discussion across multiple projects to identify the different topics and blocks that make the continuum and acting as a sharing space to shape the European landscape in the continuum integration ecosystem.

³⁸ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

³⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/task-forces/>

7 Preliminary System Architecture

This section describes the System Architecture that will enable the orchestration of applications across the cloud-continuum. Here, a Cloud-Continuum ORChestrator concept is presented, describing its main functionality, initial architecture, and design. The focus on this deliverable is to describe the general functionality of the orchestrator focusing on its capability to manage the cloud-continuum. D2.2 will, on the other hand describe its functionality with the point of view and focusing on the context of the public-private integration.

7.1 High-level requirements

After reviewing the state of the art, a set of functional requirements can be derived for a Cloud-Continuum orchestration system. This section describes this set of high-level functional requirements that will serve as a guide in the design of the overall architecture.

In relation to the applications management, the system should:

- Enable application developers to manage the lifecycle of end-to-end cloud-native applications.
- Enable the deployment of the different components of an application to be deployed across multiple computing resources, expanding across multiple domains.
- Support the simplification of the definition of end-to-end applications and the description of their components by the necessary information models to specify service composition, resource, and performance requirements. Special attention should be put in place to guarantee the energy efficiency of the deployed service.
- Support the onboarding of application packages into a structured platform application repository.
- Enable application components placement to be performed based on connectivity as well as capacity requirements.
- Allow application components access performance requirements to be specified in a declarative way.
- Monitor metrics and KPIs related to the deployed applications.

In relation to the management of the computing infrastructure, the system should:

- Integrate computing resources across multiple domains.
- Integrate computing resources from multiple providers.
- Integrate computing resources from public (hyperscalers) and private domains (on-prem).
- Abstract the multi-domain, network, and connectivity complexities between the application's internal components.
- Identify the available computing resources with their location in the network (i.e., cloud, edge, extreme edge).
- Discover and dynamically integrate available computing resources at the extreme edge which are volatile by nature.
- Configure and provision computing resources remotely.

- Monitor metrics and logs related to the infrastructure utilization, performance and health, and implement the necessary alerting mechanisms for administrators.

In relation to the management of inter-domain connectivity, the system should:

- Be able to request the establishment of connectivity from the telco operator platforms based on the application requirements.

In relation to SLA and policy enforcement, the system should:

- Be able to act in response to breaches of policy and/or missed SLAs. The use of AI/ML-assisted mechanisms as potential candidates for this kind of control should be facilitated by the platform.

In relation to the management of AI and ML, the system should:

- Enable the management of ML models lifecycle through MLOps.

In relation to security and data management, the system should:

- Implement authentication, authorization, and accountability control mechanisms to the users of the platform.
- Ensure the data privacy and security within the deployed applications, across the computing infrastructure, and through the communications inter-domain.

7.2 Concept and General Architecture

This section describes the concept and general architecture of the continuum orchestration system that will enable users to deploy end-to-end applications across computing resources distributed in multiple locations of the continuum, extending to cloud, edge and extreme edge locations and leveraging the connectivity services provided by 6G networks. **CORC**, short for **C**ontinuum-**OR**chestrator, enables the centralized orchestration of applications across a hybrid (public-private) cloud-continuum. It unifies and simplifies the deployment of applications that expand across multiple domains and benefits from the services provided by the next generation 6G networks.

Figure 4 below depicts a graphical representation of the modular CORC architecture. Each of the modules represents a specific functionality extracted from the previously described set of high-level requirements.

Figure 4. Preliminary CORC General Architecture

The concept of the CORC is based two different domains: the private vertical, including the application developer role, the system administrator manages the CORC and the users of the applications, the public telco & cloud providers domain.

The vertical domain refers to the private enterprise or industrial entity that is interested in and its ultimate goal is to leverage vertical specific applications that help solve business centric issues. This includes the users of the applications, even though they may not be part of the same enterprise or industrial entity but rather consumers of their products and services. To this effect, this entity will put in place the necessary tools and IT systems to facilitate its activity. The CORC instance falls under this category in its concept, and it is conceived as Vertical domain system that integrates and coordinates the resources from multiple public providers by interaction with open APIs offered by these third parties as well as private resources offered by other IT systems in the domain. This approach enables the flexibility of deployments required by the vertical as well as it maintains the control over the architectural strategies, evolution of the system adaptation to the development environment, enabling the integration of a hybrid cloud-continuum from the perspective and control of the application developers integrating resources from the public and private domains.

The public providers domain refers specifically to third party providers in two main categories. The first category corresponds to the providers of cloud computing resources such as hyperscalers that count with extensive deployments and services offering that can be easily leveraged by application developers without the need to deploy costly private infrastructure within the vertical domain unless necessary for the performance or data privacy gain enabled by edge deployments and required by specific applications. The second category is the network provider, and the role is principally to provide the necessary connectivity between the different tiers of the cloud-continuum, cloud, edge and extreme-edge, and the application users with the quality and performance demanded by the applications rather than simply over the public internet without control over the characteristics of the links. The end users of the vertical application would benefit from the access and connectivity fabric provided by the telco network to access

the vertical service. The network provider is key to the vertical domain in providing the expertise in network operation and management even on-premise where extensions of the telco network can be implemented to provide specific services useful to the vertical such as integrations as Non-public networks (NPNs)

CORC allows the user to request and manage infrastructure from public providers such as AWS, Azure or GCP, join existing private infrastructure at the edge and discover resources that connect to the infrastructure from the Access side using the services provided by a telco operator. CORC provides the coordination across this continuum.

CORC interface enables the user to manage 4 types of resources, namely Zones, Clusters and Providers and Applications:

- **Zone:** Zones are conceived as a combination of geographic and network locations with the aim of forming characterized groups of resources and providing the CORC with information about what tier of the cloud-continuum the resources available in such zone are considered as in direct relation with the topological location they are placed in within the operator's network. Based on this definition, the main characteristics of each zone can be established as:
 - Each zone contains information about a specific point of presence within an operator's network.
 - Each zone can be categorized as one of the following types: ExtremeEdge, Edge or Cloud zones.
 - The Cloud zone type is the default zone type when a zone is not of type Edge or Extreme Edge. This means that a zone without a specific operator's point of presence is of type cloud.
 - An Edge zone is specially characterized by the information of the operator's Network that provides Access to it such as CellId, TAC, SSID, etc... This zone type is characterized by being statically mapped to that access network information.
 - Instances of both Cloud and Edge zones maintain a list of computing resources clusters available in the zone.
 - An Extreme Edge zone represents a group of UEs with computing capabilities available and is characterized by their UE ids, their geographic location (i.e., GPS coordinates) and the information of the Access Network that provides service to them. In this instance, however, the network information is of dynamic nature but common across devices. This means an Extreme Edge access network information can be changed, mapping the behaviour of device mobility.
 - Instances of Extreme Edge zones dynamically group devices that are discovered in the zone into a single cluster of resources.
- **Computing Resources Clusters:** Each of the defined zones can be tied to one or several instances of the logical concept of Computing Resources Cluster that represents instances of groups of clustered computing resources such as Kubernetes or K3s clusters. Existing clusters in the infrastructure can be onboarded to the platform by providing the necessary detailed information about

its characteristics and credentials to manage and operate it and be associated to a specific zone with an indication of which is the provider of each cluster. A special case of Computing Resources Clusters would be those at the Extreme Edge. These clusters will be enabled by the automated discovery of devices in the network and management, being incorporated to the clusters as computing nodes while available in the network and removed when they are no longer available, due to disconnection or mobility into another zone.

- **Computing Resources Clusters Provider:** New clusters can be created and managed through the platform provided that the necessary provider API information and credentials have been provided. Each instance holds the information about the provider details, including credentials and API endpoints to interface with a provider. A provider can be PrivateOnPrem or PublicCloud.
 - PrivateOnPrem indicates that the cluster is provided privately by the vertical entity IT services.
 - PublicCloud indicates that the cluster is provided by a public cloud infrastructure provider such as AWS, Azure or GCP.
- **Telco Network Provider:** Telco network providers facilitate the underlying connectivity between zones in the continuum. When adding a zone to the continuum, specific information regarding the network point of presence serving the clusters in the zone is provided, creating a tight coupling between the available resources and the network topology location. Information regarding the API Endpoints in the operator's gateway and credentials are required for this interaction. This interface can be used to provision communication services for newly deployed applications or to steer and request information or changes to existing communications.
- **Applications:** The management applications lifecycle from onboarding to un-deployment is a key feature of the CORC. Applications are onboarded to the CORC using a specific information model to be developed that provides a detailed characterization of each of the components that form the application, including information regarding requirements and where to find the necessary artefacts (such as images), information about the topological connections between components with links characterized by performance requirements and references to the application endpoints where users will be accessing the applications. The orchestrator will make an interpretation of this information and make the necessary coordinated requests to the domain orchestrator of the clusters in each zone required to realize the instantiation of the application as well as to the operator gateway to create the connections between the zones. During the execution of the instance, the control loops in the CORC will monitor the metrics provided by the infrastructure, verify the match with the application definition and perform requests to the different providers to correct the deployments.

The control loops that observe the compliance of the deployment with the deployment are serious candidates to benefit from the use of AI/ML algorithms that can assist the decision making based on the information obtained from the metrics. This is supported by the inclusion of an AI/ML framework for MLOps in the platform that can help

automate the management of the ML pipelines lifecycle and help deploy the trained models and run its services within the orchestrator.

8 Summary and conclusions

This document includes the results of the project task *6GSMART-SP1-L2-T1.1.2: Revisión del estado del arte y diseño inicial del cloud continuo de 6GSMART, bajo la perspectiva de un desarrollador de tecnologías cloud* described in the project's execution plan.

The proliferation of 5G use cases leveraging deployments that require the use of compute resources placed at the very edge of the network and the addition of the extreme edge as a further tier that enables application developers to deploy workloads the closest possible to the data source demands for careful reflection on whether the current State of the Art mechanisms are enough for the management and orchestration of such services. To achieve the adoption of 5G and beyond technologies, new systems, mechanisms and algorithms are necessary to enable the deployment of end-to-end applications at scale. The new technologies that will define what 6G will become will front these and other challenges towards contributing to achieving the SDGs set by the UN in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

This work has tackled the concept of cloud-continuum in 6G networks. First, a study of the State of the Art with relation to the orchestration of end-to-end applications over a hybrid cloud continuum has been presented. Many research projects have started working on this topic, including aggregator initiatives like the EUCloudEdgeIoT that will help contributing the body of knowledge in the topic, setting common understandings across the EU research ecosystems, and helping to develop the open-source communities that will enable the achievement of the set goals.

Second, the document presents a high-level architecture of a system that integrates multiple domains, including private and public offerings, into a 6G cloud continuum enabled by the services consumed from telco network providers. The architecture includes the features of abstracting the application definition across the continuum, coordination of the different components orchestration across domains, discovery of resources available in the network, interfacing with the providers of the network fabric that glues the continuum together, support the inclusion of AI/ML models in the system control loops and monitoring of the utilization and health of the platform.

